

Measurement Approach to Evaluation of Ultra-low-voltage Amplifier ASICs

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Abstract: This article presents measurement circuitry and a test board developed for experimental evaluation of prototype chip samples of Fully Differential Difference Amplifier (FDDA). The device under test (DUT) is an ultra low-voltage, high performance integrated FDDA designed and fabricated in 130 nm CMOS technology. The power supply voltage of FDDA is 400 mV. The measurement circuits were implemented on the test board along with the fabricated FDDA chip to evaluate its main parameters and properties. In this work, we focus on evaluation of the following parameters: the input offset voltage, the common-mode rejection ratio, and the power supply rejection ratio. The test board was developed and verified. The test board error was measured to be 38.73 mV. The offset voltage of the FDDA was -0.66 mV. The measured FDDA gain and gain bandwidth are 48 dB and 550 kHz, respectively. Besides the measurement board, a graphical user interface was developed to simplify the control of device under test during measurements.

Keywords: Integrated circuit testing, Measurement board, Input offset voltage, Common-Mode Rejection Ratio (CMRR), Power Supply Rejection Ratio (PSRR), Fully Differential Difference Amplifier (FDDA).

1. INTRODUCTION

Integrated circuits (IC) are ubiquitous and represent a cornerstone of modern electronic systems used in number of diverse wireless applications. Ultra very large scale integration (ULSI) and new fabrication technologies provide the opportunity of developing (ultra) low-voltage and low-power analog and mixed-signal ICs, which can be used, for example, in wearable devices such as cellphones, smartwatches, and smart glasses [1]. However, as the level of integration increases greatly and ICs become more complex, requirements for IC testing also increase [2]. Test and diagnostics are very important and necessary processes of IC development and production flow, and contribute significantly to the final cost of a manufactured chip. Thus, increasing requirements for IC performance and complexity make the test process more difficult and costly too.

Nowadays, test engineers have to work more and more closely with development engineers so that they can influence specific details in the IC design to identify possible testability issues and improve test access to specific nodes/circuits in the design. We may assume that with a perfect design and fair manufacturing process, testing is unnecessary, but the opposite is true. Even a small error during the design or defect in manufacturing process can have fatal consequences for the whole IC and therefore, testing can not be underestimated [3]. For a design to be easily tested, both controllability and ob-

servability have to be ensured. Therefore, let us recall the two well-known features:

- *Controllability* - The ability to control specific parts of a design (specific nodes in the circuit) in order to set particular value of a signal. In digital electronics, this would be logic value (e.i. logic 1 or logic 0); in an analogue circuit, it would be a specific value of voltage or current.
- *Observability* - The ability to observe the response of a circuit to particular stimulus.

Ensuring controllability and observability should be done as effectively as possible so that additional test hardware do not increase the overall IC price. A traditional approach to IC testing is to finalize the design and leave it to the test engineer to identify, develop and implement a test procedure. Usually, the test is implemented in a form of software program that controls the external test equipment that is physically connected to a DUT. At this stage of test, if the test engineer finds that he or she cannot adequately test the circuit (due to limited controllability/observability), it is usually too late to fix the problem. Modern test approaches involve close collaboration between test engineers and IC designers to assess testability issues early in the design process. [4].

In this paper, methods and test circuitry for input offset voltage, CMRR, and PSRR of fabricated FDDA are presented. Firstly, the DUT chip sample description is briefly

given in Section 2. In section 3, target parameters for the evaluation are specified. Measurement methods and procedures, measurement circuitry and the developed test board together with the achieved measurement results are presented in Section 4. In the last section, conclusions are drawn.

2. DEVICE UNDER TEST (DUT)

Ordinary operational amplifier (op-amp) is an important component of many electronic devices. [5]. The op-amp design process consists of several steps: definition of specifications, selection of component sizes and bias conditions, op-amp stability compensation, simulation, and characterization of main parameters. These include open-loop gain A_{OL} , PSRR (power supply rejection ratio), CMR, (common-mode range at the input), CMRR (common-mode rejection ratio), the output voltage range, and power dissipation [6].

Usually, a differential difference amplifier (DDA) is a basic building block of recent low-voltage, low-power analog and mixed-signal ICs [7]. Similarly to operational amplifiers, the DDAs can be used in various high-performance signal processing circuits such as integrators, filters, multipliers, modulators, etc. [8]. On contrary of the ordinary operational amplifier, which has two single-ended inputs, the DDA has four inputs. The circuits with implemented DDA often provide high input impedance. However, with fully differential signal processing (typically used in low-noise applications), some basic building blocks such as level shifters and voltage followers require a dedicated DDA circuit with differential output, which is called a Fully Differential Difference Amplifier (FDDA).

The general block diagram of an FDDA is shown in Fig. 1. It consists of three main parts: **input stage**, **current-to-voltage converter**, and **output stage**. FDDA has two differential inputs that convert two differential voltages into currents. These currents are subtracted from each other and converted back to a differential voltage.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of a FDDA circuit

The differential output stage amplifies the voltage difference at the output that can be expressed as follows:

$$V_{OUT} = A[(V_{+IN1} - V_{-IN1}) - (V_{+IN2} - V_{-IN2})], \quad (1)$$

where A is the total gain, V_{+OUT1} and V_{-OUT2} are the single ended output voltages, $V_{OUT} = V_{+OUT} - V_{-OUT2}$

is differential output voltage, and $V_{+IN1} - V_{-IN1}$ and $V_{+IN2} - V_{-IN2}$ are the two input differential voltages [9].

The microscope photography of manufactured chip sample with FDDA and other supporting sub-circuits is shown in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. The photo of FDDA implemented in chip.

3. EVALUATED PARAMETERS AND MEASUREMENT METHODS

A. Input offset voltage

One of the most important parameters of operational amplifiers is the input offset voltage. This random and undesirable parameter is closely related to possible degradation of other DC or AC amplifier parameters. Therefore, measurement of this parameter is of the great importance [10]. An ideal operational amplifier has zero input offset voltage, zero input current, and infinite gain [11]. However, all operational amplifiers require a small voltage between their inverting and non-inverting inputs to compensate the mismatch of their input components caused by fabrication process variations. This required voltage is called the input offset voltage and can be modeled by a voltage source (denoted as V_{offset}) connected to the input, as shown in Fig. 3. Many techniques are known and used for compensation of the input offset voltage. One of the most common techniques is trimming during the production process [12]. Fig.4 shows a standard circuit for measuring the input offset voltage [13]. The offset voltage can be expressed as given in Equation 2.

$$V_{OS} = \frac{V_{OUT}}{1 + \frac{R2}{R1}}, \quad (2)$$

where V_{OS} is the input offset voltage, V_{OUT} is the output voltage and $1 + \frac{R2}{R1}$ is the amplifier gain.

B. Common-Mode Rejection Ratio (CMRR)

An important aspect of the differential amplifier is its ability to suppress a common signal applied to both inputs, known as the CMRR parameter. This is one of the most important performance parameters of high-precision operational amplifiers [14]. An ideal operational amplifier does not respond

Fig. 3. Modeled input offset voltage in differential operational amplifier

Fig. 4. Standard circuit for measuring input offset voltage

to voltages applied to both inputs. On the other hand, a real operational amplifier may show some response to signals applied to both inputs [15]. Input signal is applied to one input or with opposite polarity to both inputs. These signals are amplified and appear at the output. Unwanted signals appearing with the same polarity (noise) are suppressed by the differential amplifier, and there is only the desired signal at its output. This principle of the differential amplifier is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Description of CMRR parameter in the differential amplifier

CMRR parameter is defined as follows:

$$CMRR = \frac{A_{v(d)}}{A_{cm}}, \quad (3)$$

where $A_{v(d)}$ is the ratio of the differential voltage gain and A_{cm} is the common-mode gain. Properly designed differential amplifier usually has a high differential gain and a low common-mode gain, resulting in a high value of CMRR. The CMRR parameter expressed in decibels is as follows:

$$CMRR = 20 \log \left(\frac{A_{v(d)}}{A_{cm}} \right) \quad (4)$$

Alternatively, CMRR can be expressed as a change in the input offset voltage resulting from a unit change in the common-mode input voltage. This relation is expressed as follows:

$$CMRR = \frac{\Delta V_{cm}}{\Delta V_{offset}}, \quad (5)$$

where ΔV_{cm} and ΔV_{offset} are the common-mode voltage change and the offset voltage change at the input, respectively.

CMRR can be measured in several ways. The basic measurement circuit is depicted in Fig.6. It consists of a differential amplifier with four precision resistors. Signal is applied to both inputs and the output voltage change is measured. For an amplifier with infinite CMRR, the output would not change at all. To get the best result, it is important that the resistors match as closely as possible. A mismatch of 0.1% between two resistor pairs will result in a CMRR of only 66 dB (no matter how good the designed amplifier is) [16].

Fig. 6. CMRR measurement circuit

Then, CMRR can be calculated using the following:

$$\Delta V_{OUT} = \frac{\Delta V_{IN}}{CMRR} \left(1 + \frac{R2}{R1} \right), \quad (6)$$

where ΔV_{OUT} is a change in the measured output voltage, ΔV_{IN} is the input voltage change, and $1 + \frac{R2}{R1}$ is gain of the differential operational amplifier.

Fig. 8. Developed test board for evaluation of FDDA samples

C. Power Supply Rejection Ratio (PSRR)

Power supply rejection describes the ability of an amplifier to maintain its output voltage when its DC supply voltage fluctuates. When the supply voltage of an operational amplifier varies, its output voltage should not change. Description of the PSRR parameter is illustrated in Fig.7. It is shown how fluctuations in the power supply may affect the amplifier output. If a change of the power supply voltage of X volts causes the output change as a result of the differential input variation of Y volts, the PSRR parameter can be defined as X/Y ratio [17]. PSRR expressed in decibels is the following:

$$PSRR = -20 \log \left(\frac{Ripple_{input}}{Ripple_{output}} \right), \quad (7)$$

where $Ripple_{input}$ is the RMS value of the change in V_{IN} at the input, and $Ripple_{output}$ is the RMS value of the voltage change at the output [18]. The measurement setup for the PSRR parameter characterization is the same as the one used for CMRR.

Fig. 7. Influence of power supply variations in the operational amplifier

4. PROPOSED APPROACH TO DUT MEASUREMENT

The FDDA circuit was designed in Cadence design environment and experimental ASIC was prototyped in a general-

purpose 130 nm CMOS process. The required measurement circuits were implemented on a chip together with the ASIC system. Measurement circuitry serves for proof of the correct operation of each block during evaluation of chip samples using the test board. Firstly, the designed IC was simulated to verify functionality of the entire system as well as the implemented on-chip measurement circuits and the developed test board, depicted in Fig.8.

Critical and important nodes of the ASIC were connected to external measurement circuitry implemented on the test board. The whole system on the chip and measurement process are controlled by a developed digital logic unit. The control logic makes the experimental verification much easier to perform and also saves lot of package pins. Another function of the control logic is to adjust selected parameters of the FDDA. The control logic is governed by a microcontroller implemented on the test board. A graphical user interface (GUI) was also developed to simplify the experimental verification [19]. The block diagram of the whole measurement setup is shown in Fig. 9. Keysight InfiniVision DSOX2054T 4-channel digital storage oscilloscope with 5 GSps and 500 MHz of bandwidth, Keysight 33600A Series Waveform Generator, Rohde&Schwarz FSV7 signal analyzer and Rohde&Schwarz HMC 8043 3-channel power supply were employed within this setup.

Fig. 9. Block diagram of measurement setup

A. FDDA chip samples evaluation

A DC_{LOOP} schematic diagram of the developed FDDA, used for the input offset voltage measurement, is shown in Fig. 10. Gain of DC_{LOOP} for IN1+ and IN2- is given by Equation 8 and Equation 9, respectively. The value of DC_{LOOP} gain was set to 200. We chose MAX4204 device as Buff1 and Buff2, while MAX4203 device was selected as Buff3 and Buff4. The MAX4204 and MAX4203 are ultra-high-speed, open-loop buffers with high value of slew rate, high output current, low noise, and excellent capacitive load-driving capability. MAX4204 device has integrated 50 Ω termination resistors that is very convenient for driving 50 Ω transmission

 Fig. 11. AC_{LOOP} configuration of FDDA

lines. On the other hand, MAX4203 has no internal termination resistors [20]. Amplifiers AMP1 and AMP2 were represented by MAX44250 device, which is an ultra-precise, low-noise, low-drift amplifier that provides near-zero DC offset and drift through the use of patented auto-correlating zeroing techniques. The best possible circuit components have been selected in order to eliminate their undesired influence on the measured circuit [21].

 Fig. 10. DC_{LOOP} circuit of FDDA

$$GAIN(-) = -\frac{Rf_2}{R_4} \quad (8)$$

$$GAIN(+)=1+\frac{Rf_1}{R_1} \quad (9)$$

The DC_{LOOP} configuration with red interconnections (in Fig. 10) is relevant during measurement of the test board error ($ERROR_{TB}$) that was 38.73 mV . Since the measurement circuit has a large time constant, settling time of the measurement was 25 minutes. The input offset voltage of FDDA, given by Equation 11, obtained by measurement is -0.662 mV . The measurement probes were connected to the nodes labeled TP_OUT11 and TP_OUT22.

$$OFFSET = \frac{DIFF - ERROR_{TB}}{GAIN} \quad (10)$$

$$OFFSET = \frac{(OUT22 - OUT11) - ERROR_{TB}}{GAIN} \quad (11)$$

A schematic diagram of the FDDA circuit for AC_{LOOP} configuration is shown in Fig.11. The AC_{LOOP} gain for inputs IN1- and IN2+ is given by Equation 12 and Equation 14, respectively. The gain of AC_{LOOP} configuration was set to 1000. We chose MAX4204 device as Buff5 and Buff6. THS4505 device from Texas Instruments was used as a fully differential amplifier (FDA) with a bandwidth of 260 MHz [22].

$$GAIN(-) = -\frac{Rf_3}{R_2} \quad (12)$$

$$GAIN(+)=1+\frac{Rf_4}{R_3} \quad (13)$$

Block diagram of the converter from differential input to single-ended output (D2SE) is depicted in Fig.12. It was designed using the OPA3695 device [23] that is the operational amplifier with a bandwidth of 900 MHz and is suitable for instrumentation amplifiers since all three amplifiers are on the same silicon die. The offset matching between the inputs makes this configuration an attractive input stage for this application. The inputs are high impedance, with 1.2 pF capacitance to ground at each input.

The voltage gain of the instrumentation amplifier is expressed as follows:

$$Av = 1 + \frac{2R}{R_{GAIN}} \quad (14)$$

The gain of the instrumentation amplifier was set to 2 and the converter output was terminated by $50\ \Omega$ resistor. However, input impedance of a spectral analyzer was set to $50\ \Omega$ so that the measured voltage is in ratio of 1/1 (without gain).

Fig. 12. Differential input to single-ended output converter

The setup for measuring frequency response of the DUT is shown in Fig.13. The DC_{LOOP} gain was set to 200. The signal generator is connected to inputs IN1- and IN2+ via -60 dB attenuators and resistors R2 and R3. The differential output of the DUT is connected to the oscilloscope via buffers Buff1 and Buff2. Frequency response of the DUT, obtained by measurement of a single package prototype chip at temperature of 27°C , is shown in Fig. 14. The measured FDDA gain is about 48 dB and the gain bandwidth of 550 kHz was reported. The bandwidth value of 2.5 kHz was proven by measurement. Frequency response obtained by simulation is shown in Fig.15. DC gain and gain bandwidth of 43.5 dB and 758.6 kHz were achieved, respectively.

Fig. 13. Measurement setup for frequency response evaluation

Fig. 14. Frequency response of FDDA obtained by measurement

Fig. 15. Frequency response of FDDA obtained by simulation

The measurement setup for evaluation of CMRR and PSRR parameters is shown in Fig.16. It is rather complex circuit but it does not require precisely matched resistors (like the setup from in Fig. 6) that is its main advantage. In this case, the common-mode voltage is changed by switching the power supply voltages. AC_{LOOP} gain was set to 1000 with resistors $Rf3$ and $Rf4$ (see Eq. 11), and DC_{LOOP} gain was set to 200 through resistors $Rf2$ and $Rf1$ (see Eq. 10). The inputs of FDDA are connected to ground through resistors $R1$, $R2$, $R3$, and $R4$. The differential outputs of the AC_{LOOP} are fed into the D2SE converter, and then, connected to the spectrum analyzer via a $50\ \Omega$ terminating resistor. Based on the measured voltages, CMRR and PSRR parameters were calculated using Eq.6 and Eq.7, respectively. CMRR parameter was measured, when the power supply varied in phase (from positive value to negative value). For PSRR parameter measurement, the power supply was varied in the opposite phase. The obtained measured and consequently calculated results are shown in Fig.17. PSRR and CMRR parameter obtained

by simulation are depicted in Fig.18.

Fig. 16. Measurement setup for CMRR and PSRR evaluation

Fig. 17. Measured PSRR and CMRR characteristics

Fig. 18. Simulated PSRR and CMRR characteristics

B. Discussion

Comparison of main parameters of the developed FDDA obtained from simulation and measurement is shown in Table.1. From Table.1, one can observe that the value of GBW obtained by measurement decreases from 758.6 kHz to 550 kHz. Correlation of measured values for other parameters such as CMRR, PSRR also decreased. On the other hand, DC gain and the input offset voltage achieves better results than in the simulation. The deterioration of the measured parameters can be caused by different factors but most probably by fabrication process variations. Measured and simulated results were achieved at temperature of 27°C . Comparison with other DDA and FDDA amplifiers is shown in Table.2.

Table 1. Comparison of simulated and measured results of FDDA

Parameter	Simulated	Measured
DC gain	43.5dB	48 dB
GBW	758.6 MHz	550 kHz
CMRR @1kHz	91.2 dB	46 dB
PSRR @1kHz	73 dB	56 dB
Input offset	-0.880 mV	-0.662 mV

Table 2. Comparison with other DDA and FDDA amplifiers.

Parameter	FDDA[24]	DDA[25]	This work
Process[μm]	0.05	0.18	0.13
V_{DD} [V]	0.4	1.8	0.4
I_{DD} [μA]	79.6	10.7	59.8
DCgain[dB]	58.6	131	43.5
GBW[MHz]	2.31	1.1	0.7586
CMRR[dB]@1kHz	92	-	91.2
PSRR[dB]@1kHz	-	-	73

5. CONCLUSION

Measurement circuits for evaluation of the main parameters of a high-performance FDDA ASICs are presented. The input offset voltage, and CMRR and PSRR of FDDA have been the target parameters. A measurement board was developed and FDDA prototyped chip samples were evaluated using this test board. The test board error of 38.73 mV was measured. The input offset voltage of -0.662 mV was proven by measurement. The measured FDDA gain is about 48 dB. The gain bandwidth of 550 kHz and bandwidth of 2.5 kHz were measured. The total power consumption of FDDA is 59.8 μA . Obtained evaluation results show that the designed test board as well as developed measurement circuits implemented on the test board and also as a part of FDDA chips can be successfully used for evaluation of low-voltage, high-performance ASICs.

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